

The Lancet

Recovering trust in the vaccines

--Manuscript Draft--

Manuscript Number:	
Article Type:	Correspondence
Keywords:	vaccine hesitancy; covid-19 mortality; before and after mass vaccination
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Order of Authors:	Manuel Graña, PhD
Manuscript Region of Origin:	SPAIN
Additional Information:	
Question	Response
Are you are writing in response to published content in The Lancet?	Yes
Please type the full reference to that content here (for example: Cuzick J et al. Use of anastrozole for breast cancer prevention (IBIS-II): long-term results of a randomised controlled trial. Lancet 2020; 394: 117-22). as follow-up to "Are you are writing in response to published content in The Lancet?"	The Lancet. Pasteur's legacy in 21st century medicine. Lancet. 2023 Dec 17;400(10369):2157. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(22)02573-9. PMID: 36528364.
Author Comments:	Dear editor, please consider the enclosed manuscript for publication in your journal. My belief is that the correspondence raises a legitimate question on the vaccine hesitance conversation. If not properly answered, I am afraid that so called hesitant people would feel justified. Best regards Manuel Graña

Recovering trust in the vaccines

Manuel Graña

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Dear editor, I noticed from a recent editorial on your journal¹ that you assert regret the increasing vaccine hesitancy in the population. I would remind you of the excellent work done by the site ourworldindata.org² where you can confirm that many countries have achieved extremely high vaccination rates, some of them above 90% of the eligible population. So it appears that in early 2021 people was not vaccine hesitant. I think that to overcome the, in your words, increasing vaccine hesitancy, it would be necessary to explain why the summary results plotted in the accompanying figure are the natural outcome of a massive vaccination campaign (MVC) (over 13 billion doses administered). The figure plots the relative increase of covid-19 deaths per day since the start of the MVC for all countries and aggregations collected in [ourworldindata](https://ourworldindata.org)². The data and the code to generate the plot is publicly available³.

The countries that have negative values, hence some benefit, are: Andorra, Belgium, Bolivia, Central African Rep., Chad, China, Comoros, Dominican Republic, Liechtenstein, Morocco, Netherlands, Nicaragua, Nigeria, Panama, Peru, San Marino, Saudi Arabia, Sierra Leone, South Sudan, Switzerland, Tajikistan, and United Kingdom. Note that the European countries had an extraordinary mortality in March-May 2020 relative to non European countries, partially attributed to population aging, denial of care, and poor management⁴.

- 1- The Lancet. Pasteur's legacy in 21st century medicine. *Lancet*. 2023 Dec 17;400(10369):2157. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(22)02573-9. PMID: 36528364.
- 2- Edouard Mathieu, Hannah Ritchie, Lucas Rodés-Guirao, Cameron Appel, Charlie Giattino, Joe Hasell, Bobbie Macdonald, Saloni Dattani, Diana Beltekian, Esteban Ortiz-Ospina and Max Roser (2020) - "Coronavirus Pandemic (COVID-19)". Published online at [OurWorldInData.org](https://ourworldindata.org/coronavirus). Retrieved from: '<https://ourworldindata.org/coronavirus>' [Online Resource]
- 3- Manuel Graña. (2023). letter to lancet January 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7526456>
- 4- María-Victoria Zunzunegui, Fernando J.García López, Miguel Ángel Royo-Bordonada, Isabel Cienfuegos, Reply to "Integral management of COVID-19 in Madrid: Turning things around during the second wave", *The Lancet Regional Health – Europe*, Volume 3, 2021, 100065,

Fig. 1 Relative increase in deaths/day due to covid-19 after the start of the vaccination campaign in all countries and aggregations of countries with data published in OWD².

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Figure

[death_gain_after_vaccination.png](#)

